

EFFECT OF VOLTAGE AND TEMPERATURE ON THE GROWTH OF TiO₂ NANOTUBES

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Abstract: Since TiO₂ based nanotubes are widely used in industry, the anodic growth of nanotubes was studied in an organic electrolyte consisting of NH₄F and ethylene glycol at different temperatures for a period of 3 hours from 40 to 60 V. The dependence of the length and diameter of the formed nanotube on temperature was consistent with the Arrhenius equation. It can be seen that the activation energy for nanotube growth is much larger than that for diameter growth and is linearly proportional to the anodizing voltage.

Keywords: Electrochemical anodizing, voltage and temperature, electronic and ionic conductivity.

Introduction

Titanium dioxide has attracted great interest due to its non-toxicity and chemical inertness for applications in various fields, including paints, sunscreens, water separation methods [1], and lithium-ion batteries [2]. It is known that two chemical processes occur in the formation of TiO₂ nanotubes: the first is the chemical dissolution of TiO₂. The second is the formation of an oxide layer under the influence of an electromagnetic field [3]. Ruixia and her students studied the dependence of both mechanisms on the anodizing voltage, temperature, and time. They found that this electrochemical process is due to the dissolution of the oxide layer before the formation of nanotubes at high temperatures [4-5].

Experimental part

Titanium foil (thickness 100 μm, purity 99.5%, (Shuangmu Technology Co.LTD) was used as the anode and platinum was used as the counter electrode. In the anodizing process, the ratio of the anode to the cathode surface is (4:52). Since the cathode surface is much larger than the anode surface, the current density is evenly distributed on it. To clean the surface of the foil from various roughnesses and impurities, it was cleaned in a solution of HF:HNO₃:H₂O = 1:1:2 for 15 minutes (GT Sonic-D6, AC-220-240V). Then it was washed in

distilled water for another 15 minutes and dried in the open air for one hour. After that, an electrolyte consisting of 2% water, 98% ethylene glycol solution and up to 0.3% NH_4F was prepared for it. The distance between the electrodes was set at intervals of 0.5, 1.0 and 1.5 cm, respectively. During the anodizing process, the current-time curves were recorded by a computerized calculation system (potentiostat: (Model-SS-350M, S/N 21121062))

Below are diagrams of the dependence of nanotube length on temperature at different voltages of 40, 50, and 60 V (Figure 1). Bunda 40 V kuchlanishda, 12 sekda boshlangan oksidlanish jarayoni 5 μm dan boshlanib, 60 $^\circ\text{C}$ da 14 μm gacha. It can be seen that the length of the oxide layer is 4.7 μm to 10 μm starting at 50 $^\circ\text{C}$, 12 sec, 2.8 μm to 6.8 μm starting at 40 $^\circ\text{C}$, and 12 sec, 1.9 μm to 2.6 μm starting at 30 $^\circ\text{C}$ (Figure 1 (b)). This shows that the highest oxide layer is formed at 60 $^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 1. Temperature dependence diagrams of nanotube length obtained at three different voltages: (a) 40, (b) 50, and (c) 60 V.

The length of the oxide layer formed at different temperatures at 50 V is shown (Figure 1 (b)). At 60 $^\circ\text{C}$, it can be seen that it started at 12 seconds and formed from 5.3 μm to 18.3 μm . This proves that the highest oxide layer is formed at 60 $^\circ\text{C}$. At 60 V, it can be seen that the longest oxide layer is formed at 60 $^\circ\text{C}$ (Figure 1 (c)). This is due to the higher mobility of ions in the solution and the higher diffusion constant at higher temperatures.

Referanse:

1. Shankar, K., Basham, J. I., Allam, N. K., Varghese, O. K., Mor, G. K., Feng, X., & Grimes, C. A. Recent advances in the use of TiO_2 nanotube and nanowire arrays for oxidative photoelectrochemistry. (2009). The Journal of Physical Chemistry C, 113(16), 6327-6359.
2. Allam N. K., Shankar K., Grimes C. A. Photoelectrochemical and water photoelectrolysis properties of ordered TiO_2 nanotubes fabricated by Ti anodization in fluoride-free HCl electrolytes //Journal of Materials Chemistry. – 2008. – T. 18. – №. 20. – C. 2341-2348.

3. Yu, J., Fan, J., & Lv, K. (2010). Anatase TiO₂ nanosheets with exposed (facets: improved photoelectric conversion efficiency in dye-sensitized solar cells. *Nanoscale*, 2(10), 2144-2149.
4. Jennings, J. R., Ghicov, A., Peter, L. M., Schmuki, P., & Walker, A. B. (2008). Dye-sensitized solar cells based on oriented TiO₂ nanotube arrays: transport, trapping, and transfer of electrons. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 130(40), 13364-13372.
5. Wang, Jun, and Zhiqun Lin. "Anodic formation of ordered TiO₂ nanotube arrays: effects of electrolyte temperature and anodization potential." *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* 113.10 (2009): 4026-4030.

